

Binder: enabling sharing and publication of reproducible computational research

Fernando Pérez
UC Berkeley

Brian Granger
Cal Poly San Luis Obispo

Benjamin Ragan-Kelley
Simula Research, Norway

We propose to develop the Binder¹ project into a scalable, sustainable platform that will facilitate the sharing and publication of computational and data-intensive research across scientific disciplines. Our motivation is best captured in the well-known quote by Buckheit and Donoho:

“An article about computational science in a scientific publication is not the scholarship itself, it is merely advertising of the scholarship. The actual scholarship is the complete software development environment and the complete set of instructions which generated the figures.”²

Today, developments such as Github for sharing code, the rise of preprint archives beyond the ArXiv (bioRxiv, LawArXiv, engrXiv, AgriXiv, PsyArXiv, SocArxiv, etc), the easy availability of cloud computing technologies (Amazon Web Services, Google Cloud, Microsoft Azure) and data hosting repositories like Zenodo, all combine to offer the building blocks necessary to implement the vision above.

However, while possible in principle, the combination of these tools requires expertise typical of engineering operations in industry but less common in the scientific and academic world. There is a need for tools that make it straightforward for scientists to leverage the above collection of resources to share their work in a manner that supports reproducibility and collaboration. Furthermore, such tools should integrate with the scholarly publishing pipeline, so that the practice of open reproducibility extends to one of the central activities of scientific research, the creation of published manuscripts.

Binder: an early success story

Originally created by Jeremy Freeman and Andrew Osheroff at HHMI’s Janelia Research Campus, the Binder project is one such tool. Binder allows scientists to quickly create public web links and give users an easily shareable link to computational resources. Binder takes a (specially prepared) Github repository containing Jupyter notebooks and automatically constructs a Docker container that includes the original repository plus any additional dependencies. It then deploys this container automatically in the cloud, publicly accessible via a hyperlink. With this link, users can immediately access all the computational

¹ <http://beta.mybinder.org>

² Buckheit and Donoho, WaveLab and Reproducible Research, 1995

resources and the environment necessary to interact with the original project, with all code and data. Binder's power rests in its simplicity, as shown in the figure:

Turn a GitHub repo into a collection of interactive notebooks

Have a repository full of Jupyter notebooks? With Binder, open those notebooks in an executable environment, making your code immediately reproducible by anyone, anywhere.

A screenshot of the Binder web interface. It features a light gray background with a white form area. The form is titled "Build and Launch a Repository" and contains three input fields: "GitHub repo or URL" with a placeholder "GitHub repository name or link", "Git branch, tag, or commit" with a placeholder "master", and "Path to a notebook file (Optional)" with a placeholder "Path from repo root to notebook file (optional)". Below the form is a prominent blue "Launch" button.

Fig. 1. Binder interface: with a properly configured Github repository, creating a binder can be done with one click. The result is a ready-to-share Binder link pointing to a hosted Docker container in the cloud.

Binder has existed in beta status for several years now, and has seen rapid adoption from the community. It has been used in reproducing figures from high-impact papers³, teaching classes and hands-on bootcamps, and in demonstrating functionality in open-source tutorials and documentation. This growth in popularity has exposed limitations in the current version of the Binder technology, both in scalability and reliability. In recent months the JupyterHub team has worked to rebuild the backend of Binder to improve the following core features, with significant benefits being already apparent:

- Increased stability and uptime for the public Binder service
- The ability to quickly scale the computational resources available to Binder
- A streamlined implementation with more simplicity and understandable code
- A clear path towards deploying new Binder instances on a wide range of cloud providers.

³ Such as the discovery of gravitational waves by the LIGO collaboration - <https://lsc.ligo.org/tutorials>

From prototype to scalable project

This proposal details development that will solidify the technical foundation of Binder, will grow its presence in the research and publishing community, and will ensure its growth into an openly-managed, community-driven open source project that can evolve sustainably. These steps are broken down separately below.

Architectural improvements. First, we will use funds to improve the current technology in the Binder setup, continuing the recent development work described above. The new Binder code is based on Jupyter's multi-user platform, JupyterHub, optimizing reuse of common technology. This ensures a solid foundation for Binder's next phase, and all changes prompted by the Binder effort that may be required in JupyterHub will be contributed back. While Binder is a generic architecture, we will ensure that the new features serve a more diverse set of user needs by including explicit support for the three top open-source languages in data science (Python, R and Julia).

We will also provide out-of-the-box support for all the capabilities of Jupyter's next-generation interface, JupyterLab. JupyterLab provides flexibility beyond the current Jupyter Notebook user interface; we will take advantage of this to allow users to present a Binder with the desired user experience upon opening JupyterLab (e.g., direct access to the main manuscript and icons to launch the key notebooks and scripts that comprise a research compendium).

We will facilitate the inclusion of RStudio in Binder. We are in discussions with the developers of the RStudio platform: If the RStudio team is amenable to inclusion of the tool itself, we will also support the hosting of Binders that include not only Jupyter but also RStudio. Otherwise, we will provide all necessary technical hooks for RStudio to be used, but without hosting it ourselves. This would ease the path to adoption in the R community while avoiding any licensing issues.

Service improvements. We have also allocated resources to improve the hosting quality of the public Binder service. While offering large-scale hosting of executable content is financially infeasible, we estimate that with \$6,000 per month we can serve a significant community. The improvements we will develop to the platform will make it more efficient in its resource utilization, helping these funds reach more users. And we will collect detailed data on costs and resource needs, which is necessary to drive adoption of this model by third parties: for publishers to consider offering hosting of computational content with the Binder approach, they need a clear understanding of the costs involved.

Ease of use. We will improve the ease with which people can deploy their Binders, accelerating the adoption of this technology for the scientific community. These usability enhancements will allow for more widespread use of Binder's reproducible computational environments that do not depend on the public Binder service as a bottleneck. We will write extensive documentation on creating a JupyterHub instance that serves Binder links. In addition, we will incorporate server-side tools for monitoring user behavior and hardware utilization. These tools and metrics will enable Binder deployments to be a useful source of data about how users are operating in the open-source world.

We will collaborate with Tim Head, original author of the Everware project --with similar mission to Binder-- to develop common foundations that can benefit both projects and potentially lead to convergence in the future. Based on his work, we will extend Jupyterhub/Binder to allow users to execute "binders" on their own compute resources. Currently the operator of a binder instance has to provide all compute and storage resources for all users. However many academic and industry users have access to private compute resources through their affiliation. Allowing users to "bring their own compute" reduces the burden on the operator of the binder instance and allows for more efficient computing as "binders" can be launched close to where the data are hosted or on existing compute resources. Related to this is enabling users to execute "binders" on their local machines, facilitating reproducibility at all stages of the research cycle.

Community adoption. We will grow a community of users around reproducible research and open computation with the Binder service. We will host Binder training and hacking sessions in order to enable scientists to create their own Binders, and to learn about and collaborate on potential new use cases for this technology. In addition, we will create a collection of Binder repositories that serve as inspiration to scientists that wish to use this Binder in their own work.

At UC Berkeley, we will partner with the campus Research Computing team to explore how this technology can be made available to university users with both local clusters and cloud services managed through the university. Berkeley's Research Computing unit has expertise in engaging with faculty on these kinds of projects, but we'll ensure that our findings and development are widely disseminated so that researchers at institutions with less support infrastructure can also benefit.

Engagement with publishers. We want publishers, both non-profit and for-profit ones, to adopt a common standard for representing computational content, much in the way that the PDF is a standard for archiving and sharing static publications. While today authors may include Jupyter notebooks as supplementary materials, we hope to make Binder an open standard for "executable papers" across the scholarly publishing landscape. To this effect, we have begun discussions with journals who are keen to explore prototyping of these capabilities. We will target one or two partners during the duration of this effort, to develop a viable approach that can then be expanded to other publishers in the future.

As part of this effort, we will develop a formal specification of what a Binder-compliant Github repository should be. Establishing a machine-readable description of the contents and resources necessary to transfer, instantiate and execute a Binder will aid in the discoverability and impact of Binder.

By engaging with publishers and developing formal, open standards (on top of others like PDF and Jupyter Notebooks), we can achieve dual goals: to provide a viable business model for publishers (e.g. the hosting of premium executable content) while retaining the openness of the core standards so that scientists remain in control of their content. With a standard for Binders, it should be possible to move a Binder from a publisher's website to a university cluster or cloud account, preventing publisher lock-in (much like one can read a PDF on a journal website or download it for personal reading).

Project governance. We will develop a model for the community to establish an open governance for Binder. Given that the project is not only a software tool but also intends to drive change in practices of scholarly communication, engagement with the broader scientific community and publishers will be vital

to its success, and decisions will be required where the technical and the social intersect. We will seek engagement with multiple stakeholders to develop a governance model that supports our core goals of sustainable technical development, open science, reproducible research and executable scholarly communications.

Team

The project team is composed of, in alphabetical order (a * next to a name indicates no budget is being requested for that person):

- Aaron Culich*, software architect with UC Berkeley Research Computing
- Brian Granger*, co-PI at CalPoly San Luis Obispo
- Chris Holdgraf, postdoctoral researcher at UC Berkeley
- Yuvi Panda, engineer at UC Berkeley
- Fernando Perez*, lead PI at UC Berkeley
- Benjamin Ragan-Kelley, co-PI at Simula Research Lab in Oslo, Norway
- Carol Willing, engineer at Cal Poly San Luis Obispo
- Tim Head, consultant from Everware Project.
- To be hired - Research Intern at Simula Research Lab

This team has extensive expertise in all areas of the proposed work, and a proven track record of effective collaboration. PI Perez had discussions with Jeremy Freeman in 2015 as part of the creation of Binder, and has co-led the development of Project Jupyter. Subcontracts will be issued to co-PIs Brian Granger at CalPoly and Benjamin Ragan-Kelley at Simula, who have worked alongside Perez on IPython, then Jupyter, since approximately 2005. At CalPoly, engineer Carol Willing will partner with Ragan-Kelley on the implementation of features based on JupyterHub, which they already co-develop and therefore know intimately. They will be joined by the team at UC Berkeley, composed of engineer Yuvi Panda, architect Aaron Culich and postdoctoral researcher Chris Holdgraf, who have already worked on the new Binder prototype described above. We will also work with, as a consultant, the original project lead for Everware, a platform that was originally created at CERN independently of Binder but which pursues similar goals and is also based on Jupyter technology. This collaboration will help the two projects share technical work, and could potentially lead to integrating them more fully in the future. Dr. Head will contribute tools and integrations scientists to execute their Binders on local computational resources.

Finally, we note that all our recent work on the Binder platform has been in close partnership with its original author, Dr. Jeremy Freeman. Dr. Freeman is now leading computational biology at the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative (CZI) and currently has limited bandwidth to participate directly in our research. But we will maintain a regular dialog with him and his new team on all developments, will include him in all governance discussions, and will welcome any participation he and his team may have in the future, as time permits.

Risk Assessment

Our a team combines all the necessary expertise and track record to ensure technical success. While technical complications are not impossible, given our experience and the existence of both the original Binder prototype and the current re-implementation, we don't foresee major obstacles on that front. Some of the more novel efforts to standardize and generalize metadata around executable containers may present challenges both technical and in terms of adoption. But a prototype implementation, even with limitations, appears viable within our timeframe and roadblocks encountered here would not block the entire project.

The most significant risk we foresee is in the adoption by publishers: for that to happen, organizations beyond our control will need to embrace both our ideas and our technical approach. While we have received multiple expressions of interest by publishers regarding these ideas, we can not guarantee that in the end they will be willing to commit to our vision.

Budget Justification

The bulk of the budget corresponds to the salaries of all research personnel. Adequate travel support has been included in the plan for the participants.

For hosting the public, unauthenticated mybinder.org cloud service, we have allocated \$6,000 per month. This is sufficient to meet our goal of providing a community baseline service and accrue usage analytics to inform long-term resource needs and business models.

We have allocated \$25,000 for hosting a 2-day workshop where we will invite multiple stakeholders, both developers in the open source and open science world as well as industry publishers. We plan on hosting this in the summer of 2018. The goals of this workshop will be to:

- Present the technical architecture of the system.
- Help others adopt it in their own workflows.
- Gather further user-driven requirements and use cases.
- Engage with more scholarly publishers, based on our experience by that time with our early adopters.
- Solidify the project's governance model.

Impact and future developments

Together, these goals will significantly improve the ability of Binder to meet the needs of the scientific community, in support of an efficient workflow of open and reproducible science. The proposed research will spark further growth and new uses within the Binder community and will ensure that the service remains a productive, fruitful tool for years to come. Adoption of these open practices in the publishing

community could have large-scale, systemic impacts in improving reproducibility of scientific publications, and could support novel forms of knowledge discovery (once the atomic unit of collaboration isn't just a PDF but a computational entity with rich, machine-readable semantics).

Key outcomes

Date (outputs only)	OUTCOME TABLE	
	<i>OUTCOME 1: Easy, reproducible workflows are available via Binder for scientists to deploy containers with Python, R, and Julia environments.</i>	
2018 02-01	<i>Output 1.1: New technical features enhance the experience of using Binder for reproducible computational workflows.</i>	
	1.1.1	Provide user-facing UI for statistics and Binder health monitoring
	1.1.2	Support use of Binder with applications that complement the Jupyter stack (JupyterLab/Notebook), such as RStudio, etc.
	1.1.3	Create technical solutions towards connecting Binder instances with data that is stored outside of the repository.
2018 06-01	<i>Output 1.2: Binder user community has increased in size and diversity.</i>	

	1.2.1	Create documentation and training materials for bootcamps on teaching scientists how to create / deploy Binder-compliant repositories.
	1.2.2	Host several Binder training sessions / workshops to increase adoption and community input
	1.2.3	Add a gallery of canonical examples as Binder repositories for each language. Include a set of “Binder-compliant practices” in each language to demo w/ Binder.
	1.2.4	Support novel interactive publications through collaboration with publishers (eLife, mSystems, etc)
	1.2.5	Collect use-case information in order to develop a roadmap to meet new demands for future development.
2017 11-01	Output 1.3: mybinder.org is sustainable	
	1.3.1	Increase the computational resource available to the public binder to support higher levels of usage
	1.3.2	Fund sustainable deployment and maintenance of mybinder.org (e.g., compute time, personnel time for issue triage and incident response)
	1.3.3	series of blog posts throughout the year documenting the pilot findings

	1.3.4	Establish governance model with clear guidelines for participation, in service of long-term mission.
2018 08-01	Output 1.4: Binder deployments other than the public Binder are actively used	
	1.4.1	Develop infrastructure metrics and logging for deployments
	1.4.2	Allow users to deploy Binder locally from binder-compliant repositories.
	1.4.3	Create documentation and instructions for deploying custom Binder servers via JupyterHub